

The Impact of Gender Segregation on Individual Identity and Societal Roles

Anushka Raheja

Chinguacousy Secondary School

HSE4M: Equity & Social Justice: From Theory To Practice

Ms. Ramandeep Singh

April 25, 2025

Male and female struggles in the real world:

This paper explores the impact of culturally influenced gender stereotypes and norms imposed on individuals. Female and male struggles already exist in the real world, and societal implications of gender roles make these struggles harder to combat. Although significant efforts have been made to promote gender equality and fair treatment of men and women, culturally enforced norms continue to reinforce these stereotypes, which harm the efforts of gender activists who struggle to achieve structural equality in the system. From birth, individuals are conditioned to internalize the segregation of gender roles and abide by the societal norms, making it harder to unlearn the conditioning and accept a liberal approach to equality. While women's rights have advanced significantly over the past decades, practices and beliefs that provide a hierarchical privilege to men and masculinity still exist (Cislighi & Heise, 2019). Additionally, while women are provided with formal and fundamental rights all over the world, they are still deprived of economic privileges.

Men are also affected by patriarchy. Men frequently face emotional repression due to societal expectations. In Foy (2023), society expects men to refrain from showing emotions other than anger. Crying is often considered “feminine”, and men are frequently discouraged from expressing emotional vulnerability through crying. Men are also looked down upon for performing domestic roles, and it is normalized for them to have a distant relationship with their children.

Role of culture and societal conditioning in segregating gender roles and forming stereotypes:

It has been established in (Bedew, 2025) that culture plays a significant role in defining human values and beliefs, forming strong societal norms. Generally speaking, social norms are rules of action shared by people in a given society or group; they define what is considered normal and acceptable behaviour for the members of that group. Therefore, in this aspect, gender norms are followed not just due to personal beliefs, but also by what society considers appropriate or inappropriate. Gender norms are the social rules and expectations that keep the gender system intact and play a major role in harboring gender inequality.

For instance, a girl may feel pressured to be soft-spoken, not because she inherently feels that way, but because these traits are expected and socially rewarded in her community. Similarly, boys may face ridicule for being soft-spoken or acting “feminine”, leading them to gravitate towards “tougher” or dominant actions. This systemic conditioning explains why gender roles are so deeply embedded. Systematic gender inequalities have always existed in our society. Individuals resonate with societal pressure of gender roles imposed differently on each gender, which limit people's freedom of expression. Such differences are socially, not biologically determined.

As adolescents grow up to become men and women, they engage with and construct their gender-based understandings of what it means to be a boy or a girl (Blum et al., 2017). Adolescence is a prime age for development, and when kids form beliefs and values of their own. Kids from a young age are exposed to these stereotypes, which shape their mindset about gender norms for life. Around the world, pubertal boys are viewed as predators and girls as potential

targets and victims. Messages such as “do not sit like that,” “do not wear that,” “do not talk to him,” and “boys will ruin your future” support the gender division of power, and affect youth while promoting sex segregation to preserve girls’ sexuality. In various places, girls internalize these norms to an even greater extent than boys. As one girl in Assuit, Egypt, noted:

“A girl cannot go out as she wishes because she is a girl, and if a girl comes home late, her parents would shout at her, but it is okay for a guy.” (Blum et al., 2017).

At a young age, in several parts of South Asia, women noted that they found their body as burdensome and at risk and felt the need to cover up, while in parts of Baltimore, women claimed that their primary asset was their bodies and they need to look appealing—but not too appealing (Luscombe, 2017). This duality, when it comes to gender expectations, shows the social dynamic of how different cultures condition individuals to pertain to gender roles differently, while also demonstrating that these norms intersect at a common fact that gender segregation has harmful effects.

Gender segregation and its effects on individuals in Middle Eastern countries:

A thread on Reddit on r/arabs (“r/Arabs Men Here, You Sometimes Feel That You Can’t Express Emotions?”, 2020) discusses and gathers individual opinions about the taboo of male expression of emotions in the Middle East, in the subreddit. As a person advocates that emotional stoicism is more desirable for men, and is a cultural responsibility:

“It’s normal in any conservative society. Women seek strong, confident men who don’t need to question their motives, display sorrowful woe, or ask for help (at least not publicly). I’m not saying whether it’s good or bad, but this is the nature of all conservative societies. Even in the more feminized liberal West, women still, for the most part, seek a strong, confident man to lead them. Our job has always been to lead, not rule and punish, but lead our families, our societies, and protect our traditions. Once you start going down a rabbit hole of not wanting to be like that, we lose our immense possessiveness over our traditions and culture. Emotions are not for men in my family at all. The only emotions we have in front of others are anger or humor.”

This quote highlights the normalization of emotional suppression as a part of societal conditioning and the burden of responsibility men worldwide presume as “protectors” of their culture. The adverse effects of such conditioning frequently lead to the normalization of expressing emotional pain through violent behaviors and contribute to the rise of mental health issues.

Moreover, Middle Eastern societies prefer men to be the traditional breadwinners and women to bear the domestic and caregiver roles. Therefore, men choosing domestic roles such as stay-at-home fathers are often looked down upon, especially in the Middle Eastern society (Lee & Lee, 2018). The expectation that men should withhold economic responsibility for the house places an unwanted burden on many individuals regardless of their preferences. Similarly, independent women are less likely to be viewed as suitable partners for marriage in Middle Eastern societies, as noted by Elamin and Omair (2010):

Women as caregivers and homemakers and men as breadwinners and leaders are stereotypes that dictate the appropriateness of various occupations for females and males (Schreiber, 1998). Women's worlds are thought to include a particular type of labor, namely care for others (concerning bodies, minds, and spirits) and maintenance of relationships, whereas men's worlds emphasize individual thought, independent achievement, and success based on competition and hierarchy (Maier, 1997). (p. 5)

These stereotypical roles set limitations on personal freedom and affect individuals' ability to pursue a life they truly desire.

Middle Eastern societies are also known for the social repression of women, limiting young girls from education in Afghanistan. Imposing strict dress codes and coercing women to cover their identities, in many cases against their will, is also a socially enforced gender norm. Iran's dress code laws led to the killing of Mahsa Amini, a woman protesting against laws that limit female autonomy and oppression. (Amnesty International, 2023). Early or child marriage of women in parts of Afghanistan and rural areas across the Middle East is also normalized as a part of conditioning women into accepting the socially acceptable domestic sectors. (UNICEF, 2022). These systemic expectations to stay limited within domestic roles make women in the Middle Eastern-North African (MENA) region more vulnerable to mental health issues. (Eloul et al., 2009)

Gender segregation and its effects on individuals in Africa

Gender segregation in African societies has been shaped over the decades since post apartheid. Male members of society are generally expected to be the family's sole breadwinners, similar to many other societies. Their worth is often tied to employment, with unemployment leading to struggles with confidence, self-criticism, and, in some cases, resorting to violence (Ratele, 2015). African men tend to suppress emotional expressions, which are viewed as "feminine" or as a Western concept. Violence and aggression are normalized and considered to be a masculine form of expression. African men struggle with the burden of being recruited into militia groups during conflict and are often separated from their families at a young age to participate in the military. (Christopher M. Faulkner, 2024). The societal expectations to remain "tough" and persist as the dominant figure in the household lead many individuals to shift to substance abuse. Apartheid has played a major role in shaping the role of African men who are stereotypically portrayed as threats, subjecting their masculinity to criminalization and control.

Women in the African region face a triple burden of racism, classism, and patriarchy. Women in African societies are encouraged to give up education and careers to prioritize marriage and engagement in domestic roles. African women are frequently subject to hypersexualization, with the historic example of Sara Baartman demonstrating the internalized racial and sexual objectification of African women (Parkinson, 2016). Africa has one of the highest rates of femicide, which again shows the societal influence to preserve institutionalized patriarchy (Human Rights Watch, 2024). Women in Africa are also expected to be obedient and submissive, being more inclined towards motherhood. Infertility is heavily stigmatized in African societies. Womanhood is often equated to motherhood, sacrificing their identity. The

book, *Male Daughters, Female Husbands*, by Ifi Amadiume, argues that pre-colonial African society was egalitarian and that apartheid and Western and European colonization have made African women vulnerable to inequality. (GradeSaver, n.d.)

Gender segregation and its effects on individuals in South Asia:

Similar to the Middle Eastern and African societies, South Asian men are often expected to fit into the roles of being the sole earner of the family and are discouraged from pursuing careers in the creative fields. The pressure to bear the financial responsibilities of the household from a young age causes individuals to struggle with a lack of freedom of choice. Men in South Asian societies are often inclined towards the expectation to remain emotionally stoic and independent from a young age, and are discouraged from forming emotionally intimate relationships with friends and family. This often results in undiagnosed mental illnesses, ultimately giving rise to growing suicide rates in South Asia (Yamini, 2024). From a young age, parents invest emotionally in daughters while expecting sons to be emotionally independent and “strong,” causing deep-rooted emotional neglect.

Female aspirations in the South Asian society are often limited to marriage and domestic roles. Daughters are often perceived as burdens, contributing to practices like dowry (Bhopal, 1997). Women are expected to move in with their husband's family after marriage, highlighting the lack of independence in the society, making single mothers or divorced women socially stigmatized and scrutinized. As mentioned in Sivakumar and Manimekalai (2021):

Also, women are trained not to challenge discrimination, subordination, exploitation, and subjugation at various levels in the system. These norms restrict women from having aspirations beyond marriage. Similarly, for men, gender norms are constructed around masculinity, and a man's sense of self hinges on his ability to control women. Until the daughter is married, her protection and chastity are considered as a mark of the father's honour and masculinity.

The above extract provides evidence of the regulation of systematic inequality practiced in South Asian communities, limiting female autonomy and infantilizing women by limiting their capability to make personal decisions and assert independence. Women are often expected to be the caregivers and childbearers in society, tying their social value to motherhood. Women are also viewed as symbols of family honor, and similar to Middle Eastern societies, are expected to cover their bodies to avoid “dishonor” to their family. In the paper (Gill, 2009), Aisha Gill talks about the significance of honour in South Asian households and the social performance of women tied to the honour.

In South Asian communities, ‘honour’ (Urdu: izzat) is highly valued; it is in the conduct, actions, and social performances of women that families attain ‘honour’ and prestige. The family ‘honour’ must be preserved at all costs: family interests take precedence over individual interests. As izzat relies on the behavior of women, safeguarding the family izzat can also be viewed as a means of exercising social control over women's bodies and behavior.

Furthermore, the expectation to be submissive results in the role of women in the household being limited to domestic roles such as caregiving and childbearing, with lesser involvement in household decisions compared to the male members of the family.

Gender segregation and its effects on individuals in Western Society:

Western society coined the term Toxic masculinity in the 1980s. It refers to the attitude men are conditioned to adopt, which negatively impacts them and society. The expectations to be financially independent and provide for their families lead to men in Western society facing insecurity of feeling “left behind,” especially with the rise of feminism and economic independence for women. The insecurity often contributes to the exaggeration of masculine traits to overpower women in sectors, and causes toxic masculinity to stay intact. As Connell (1995/2005) outlines in her theory of hegemonic masculinity,

Hegemonic masculinity can be defined as the configuration of gender practice that embodies the currently accepted answer to the problem of the legitimacy of patriarchy, which guarantees (or is taken to guarantee) the dominant position of men and the subordination of women.

Western culture rewards a narrow definition of manhood, rooted in dominance, control, and emotional repression, leaving men who deviate from this model struggling with masculine identity and emotional well-being.

Women in the West struggle with the expectation of bearing a double burden, i.e., bearing the responsibility of an employee and the domestic caretaker. Ethically, Women’s involvement in the workplace puts an equal responsibility on both men and women of the family to manage domestic roles, yet, as cited (Sourabh Batar et al., 2021).

As women are increasingly involved in employment outside the home, men have an opportunity to become more involved in the care and socialization of children. But social surveys conducted in the same fields indicate that men find little time to devote to either socializing children or to share the family burden with their wives.

This societal expectation for women to fundamentally pursue the domestic sector leads to a burden on them to pursue a larger share of domestic responsibilities, also undervaluing their contribution in the economic sector of the household. While Western society is considered modernized when it comes to a more inclusive role and representation of women in society and economy, including more political and corporate representation of women, it is established in the research (AAUW, 2022) that there is still a persisting gender wage gap. They are also prone to underrepresentation in financial and commercial sectors, popularly known as the glass ceiling effect, which limits the possibility of women succeeding in the workplace and holding higher or equal authoritative positions as men (Gabaldon et al., 2024). The persisting unethical conduct remarks the presence of systematic gender inequalities in the patriarchal society, which discourages female interference outside domestic sectors.

In conclusion, while gender segregation manifests differently across cultures, as seen in the Middle Eastern, South Asian, African, and Western societies, it universally enforces patriarchy on both men and women. As a result, it affects everyone, regardless of their gender, both emotionally and economically, by limiting individual autonomy. By recognizing and questioning the origin of these practices, one can unlearn the societal conditioning and contribute to bringing a positive change. To achieve an ultimately egalitarian society which promotes individual autonomy, it is important to eradicate these deeply rooted and socially accepted gender norms, which play a significant role in perpetuating gender inequality, and sabotaging the impact of the initiatives taken by gender rights advocates and activists for achieving gender equality.

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